

Caregiving Preparedness and Burden of Caregivers of Persons Receiving Hemodialysis

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Abstract

Background: Caregivers of persons receiving hemodialysis require close and continuous assistance, as they face challenges in physical, emotional, psychological, social, and economic aspects, resulting in a significant caregiving burden. **Methodology:** This descriptive correlational study aimed to explore the caregivers burden and caregiving preparedness of caregivers for persons receiving hemodialysis, and to examine the relationship between caregiving preparedness and caregivers burden. A total of 144 caregivers were purposively selected from those providing care to persons receiving hemodialysis at Guangxi Hospital, People's Republic of China. Data were collected using questionnaires, which included a general information form of the caregivers, a caregiving preparedness assessment tool, and a caregiver burden assessment tool. Descriptive statistics and Spearman's correlation coefficient were used for data analysis. **Results:** The results revealed that caregivers experienced a relatively high caregiver burden ($\bar{X} = 50.25$, $SD = 17.65$). The caregiving burden in specific aspects were as follows: relationship burden ($\bar{X} = 13.33$, $SD = 5.45$), emotional burden ($\bar{X} = 14.97$, $SD = 6.07$), social and family life burden ($\bar{X} = 7.67$, $SD = 4.37$), financial burden ($\bar{X} = 2.91$, $SD = 1.29$), and loss of control over one's own life ($\bar{X} = 11.38$, $SD = 3.34$). Caregiving preparedness was found to be low ($\bar{X} = 14.21$, $SD = 5.24$). Additionally, a moderate negative correlation was found between caregiving preparedness and overall caregiving burden ($r = -0.474$, $p < 0.01$). Moderate negative correlations were also found between caregiving preparedness and specific aspects of caregiving burden: relationship burden ($r = -0.373$, $p < 0.01$), emotional burden ($r = -0.444$, $p < 0.01$), social and family life burden ($r = -0.430$, $p < 0.01$), financial burden ($r = -0.427$, $p < 0.01$), and loss of control over one's own life ($r = -0.361$, $p < 0.01$). **Conclusion:** This study provides fundamental information for nurses to better understand and prepare caregivers in order to reduce the caregiving burden for persons receiving hemodialysis.

Keywords: Burden of Caregivers, Caregiving Preparedness, Caregiver, Hemodialysis.

INTRODUCTION

Hemodialysis (HD) is a therapeutic procedure that uses a dialysis machine and a special filter called an artificial kidney or a dialyzer to continuously remove extra waste products from body, such as creatinine, urea, nitrogen, fluid, and electrolytes. This renal replacement therapy helps individuals with end stage renal disease (ESRD) to maintain the balance of acid-base, fluid and electrolyte, such as potassium, calcium and sodium, as well as control the blood pressure (Elliott, 2000; Himmelfarb & Ikizler, 2010; Murdeshwar & Anjum, 2020). The HD utilization grew by 269% from 2012 to 2023, with significant regional disparities in access to treatment of 916,647 cases (Chinese National Center for Quality Control of Nephrology, 2024).

In Guangxi, a southeastern region, 468 out of 850 hospitals were equipped for HD by 2022, reflecting a growing demand for dialysis services (Guangxi Autonomous Region Health Commission Department, 2023).

ESRD imposes a substantial burden on HD patients, affecting their physical, psychological, emotional, financial, and family social well-beings. Common symptoms include fatigue, chest pain, itching, bone pain, and complications such as anemia, sleep disorders, and gastrointestinal issues. Patients often face emotional challenges like depression and anxiety, which further strain family dynamics and create ongoing caregiving needs. These above symptoms and signs, along with the financial burden of dialysis, significantly reduce quality of life. Financially, hemodialysis costs are high, with patients in China facing up to ¥1,027,000 in treatment expenses over eight years (Wang et al., 2018). Family caregivers play a critical role in managing daily care for ESRD patients, which includes physical tasks, emotional support, and medical monitoring. Caregivers often experience stress due to the demands of care, including managing symptoms, administering medications, and ensuring dietary restrictions (Li et al., 2017; Liu, 2017; Zheng & Duan, 2018). This caregiving role can strain caregivers' social and family lives and increase financial pressures.

Preparedness, as defined by Archbold (1992), refers to perceived preparedness of the caregiving role, including providing physical care, emotional needs, finding out about and setting up services, stress management, activities for entertainment, responding to and handling emergency, and getting help and information from the health care system and the overall preparedness (Archbold et al., 1992). Well-prepared caregivers are better equipped to manage the demands of caregiving, leading to improved mental and physical health. Caregiver burden, refers to the extent to which caregivers perceived their emotional, physical health, social life and financial status as suffering as a result of caring for their relatives (Zarit et al., 1986). It is often assessed across five domains as relationship burden, emotional burden, social and family burden, financial burden, and loss of control over one's life. The relationship between caregiver burden and preparedness has been discussed. Low to moderate preparedness negatively affects caregivers' psychological well-being, leading to anxiety and depression, while higher preparedness is linked to better well-being.

A Chinese study of 120 family caregivers of hemodialysis patients found that 67.5% experienced moderate to high levels of burden, and greater caregiver preparedness was associated with lower burden (Li et al., 2017). Other studies indicated that greater caregiver preparedness predicts lower burden and reduced depression among caregivers of individuals with disabilities (Uhm et al., 2023) and in palliative care settings (Karabulutlu et al., 2022). In China, family caregivers face unique burdens compared to Western caregivers.

A study found that primary caregivers are mainly spouses (28.69%), children (20.25%), and other relatives or friends (32.06%), with 65% providing care alone. Most caregivers are female (66.24%) and under 45 years old (37.55%) (Wang et al., 2021). Caregivers of palliative patients spend an average of 8.3 hours per day on caregiving tasks, with 25.3% providing over 13 hours daily (Rhee et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2021). However, caregiver preparedness varies significantly due to factors like education, income, healthcare support, and cultural differences.

In less developed regions like Guangxi, many caregivers lack training, resources, and a less structured healthcare system, leading to feelings of inadequacy and increased stress (Zeng et al., 2015). Therefore, enhanced support systems to improve caregivers' preparedness in areas such as physical care, emotional support and emergency management is a clear urgent need, especially for informal caregivers of ESRD patients undergoing hemodialysis. There is currently a gap in research examining caregivers burden and caregiving preparedness among outpatient caregivers of ESRD patients in Guangxi, China. While some Chinese studies have explored related topics, such as physical

and mental strain (Li et al., 2017), which haven't fully addressed the aspects about social family, financial, or loss of control one's life.

Another study from Guangzhou (Qiu, 2020) found overall burden score (\bar{X} = 38.75, SD = 6.75) and preparedness score (\bar{X} = 2.25, SD = 0.59), and weak correlation between burden and preparedness (r_s = -0.283, p = 0.000), but it didn't fully assess updated five domains of burden regarding about relationship, emotion, social family, finance and sense of control, which may not fully capture all domains in the original context. Moreover, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, which affected 22.4% of Chinese HD patients due to severe trauma-related stress symptoms and psychological distress caused by lockdowns and related policies (Xia et al., 2021), introduces another layer of complexity, especially when considering pre- and post-pandemic caregiving conditions. Additionally, cultural and regional differences across various areas further complicate the situation, such as those found in Guangxi, an ethnically diverse autonomous region primarily governed by the Zhuang minority, further influence caregivers' experiences and confidence levels. There is also a noticeable lack of updated research on caregiver burden and preparedness in less-developed regions like Guangxi, which this study aims to address. By focusing on outpatient informal caregivers, this study provides a clearer understanding of challenges faced by family caregivers.

Research Objectives

- 1) To explore caregivers burden and caregiving preparedness of caregivers for persons receiving hemodialysis in Guangxi, China.
- 2) To examine the relationship between caregiving preparedness and caregivers burden.

Research Conceptual Framework

The perception framework was based on literature review. Individuals receiving hemodialysis often experience functional dependency, physical symptoms, psychological and mental stress, social isolation, and financial difficulties. These challenges not only affect the ESRD patients but also create significant burden on their family caregivers. Burden is defined as the extent to which caregivers perceived their emotional or physical health, social life and financial status as suffering because of caring for their relatives (Zarit et al., 1986), recently measured by five domains including relationship strain, emotional well-being, social and family life, financial impact, and loss of control over one's life. Caregiving preparedness is an essential factor influencing burden. Defined as perceived readiness of caregiving role (Archbold et al., 1990), preparedness encompasses the ability to meet physical and emotional needs, find out about and set up services, create a positive caregiving environment, manage emergencies, and seek support and information from the health care system. When caregivers are well prepared for caregiving, they tend to be more confident in caregiving roles, efficiently control the patients' situation, and easily solve the problems, by which lessening the overall burden. This framework provides a structured approach to understanding the dynamics between patient needs, caregiver burden, and the role of caregiving preparedness, and underscores the importance of interventions aimed at enhancing preparedness among family caregivers to alleviate burden and improve caregiving outcomes.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive correlational study. The targeted population was the family caregivers of persons receiving HD in the hemopurification area of the provincial HD center in Guangxi hospital, People's Republic of China.

Sample

The desired sample size was determined by calculating using Yamane's formula (1973) at the level of significance $\alpha=0.05$. Therefore, a total of 144 family caregivers were included. The convenience sampling method has been applied to choose the participants who meet the recruitment criteria. The recruitment criteria include the participates of caregivers: a) mostly involved in taking care of the dependent and independent patients during hemodialysis and at home, with caring time ≥ 6 months (Fu, 2018; Shih et al., 2019; Zhang & Jiang, 2009); b) spend the longest hours to takes care of the patient in one day. If there are several caregivers at the same time, designate a main caregiver or person who is responsible for management as the main caregiver; c) without payment or any salary from the care receiver; d) proficient in Chinese, and able to read and answer the questionnaires; and e) voluntarily participate in this study and sign the informed consent.

Research Instruments

This study applied three questionnaires, including a demographic data form, the Chinese version of Preparedness for Caregiving Scale, and the Chinese version of Zarit Burden Interview.

Demographic data form designed by the researcher based on literature review. The 14-item survey collects general information about caregivers including age (year), gender, marital status, relationship status, employment status, educational level, income level (CNY/month), frequency of transportation (week), duration been caregiver (month), length of caregiving, insurance and co-morbidities of the care receiver, and number of dependents.

The Chinese version of Preparedness for Caregiving Scale (CPCS) was originally developed by Archbold et al. (1990) and translated by Shyu et al. (2010) to measure the perceived preparedness of caregivers across eight caregiving domains regarding physical needs, psychological and emotional needs, related services, stress management, activities for pleasure, managing emergencies, getting useful information and overall preparedness (Archbold et al., 1990; Shyu et al., 2010). The questionnaire is a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 0 (Not at all prepared) to 4 (Very well prepared), with overall score ranges from 0 to 32. The total score indicated an average of the responses. The higher scores indicate a greater perceived level of preparedness. The CPCS has good validity, with each item and the total score was 0.706 to 0.839 ($P<0.01$) (Liu et al., 2016), and high reliability with the Cronbach's alpha coefficient reported as 0.92 (Shyu., et al., 2010), and 0.83 in this study.

The Chinese version of Zarit Burden Interview (CZBI) was developed by Zarit and held rights by Mapi Research Trust to evaluate caregivers' burden faced (Lu et al., 2009; Zarit et al., 1986), though 22 items categorized into five domains, including burden in relationship (item 1, 8, 11, 14, 18, 20), emotional well-being (item 2, 4, 5, 9, 10, 21, 22), social and family life (item 3, 6, 12, 13), finances (item 15) and loss of control over one's life (item 7, 16, 17, 19). Each item is scored on a 5-point Likert scale, range from 0 to 4, with a total score range from 0 to 88, reflecting the cumulative burden experienced by caregivers. There are no universal cut-off scores and the best way to explain the experienced ZBI score is to assess the variability within a sample and changes over time for the individuals providing caregiving. The higher reported score refers to greater experienced caregiver burden. The CZBI has shown good validity, as correlation with other measures are 0.53-0.73 ($p<0.01$) (Yap., 2010) and high internal consistency with Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.87 (Lu et al., 2009) and 0.94 in this study.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) 19.0, with significance level set at 0.05. Each variable was tested by using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test for normality distribution, with both preparedness and burden were normal distributed. Descriptive

and inferential statistics were applied. Frequency, percentage, and/or range, mean, and standard deviation were used for demographic data, preparedness and each item of CPCS. The Spearman’s correlation coefficient was used to assess the correlation between preparedness and burden, as well as five domains of burden.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Part I: Demographics

Among the 144 participants, most family caregivers were female (62.50%), married (97.22%), and parents (50%). The average age was 52.38 years (SD = 14.23), with 36.11% being older adults. Regarding employment, 39.58% worked part-time (20 hours/week), and 35.42% were unemployed. Regarding education, 28.48% had completed junior middle school, and 21.53% had finished primary school. Most caregivers (47.92%) earned ¥2,000 – ¥5,000 monthly. In caregiving, 75% (108 caregivers) transported patients to hemodialysis three times a week, spending over 15 hours per week (59.73%) with a mean of 17.65 hours (SD = 7.98). Half (54.17%) had been caregivers for over 24 months, with an average duration of 36.3 months (SD = 35.58). Regarding healthy status, 68.8% reported good health, and most caregivers cared for one (49.31%) or two (26.38%) dependents. Additionally, 71.53% of patients had conditions beyond ESRD, and 98.61% were insured under provincial, municipal, or NRCI insurance. Detailed data are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Caregivers of Persons Receiving Hemodialysis in Nanning City, Guangxi, China (n=144)

Demographic Characteristics	Frequency(n)	Percentage(%)
Age (years) (\bar{X} =52.38 SD= 14.23 Range 21-79)		
20-39 years old	30	20.83
40-59 years old	62	43.06
60-79 years old	52	36.11
Gender		
Male	54	37.50
Female	90	62.50
Marital Status		
Married	140	97.22
Widowed	3	2.08
Divorced	1	0.70
Relationship to patient		
Spouse	1	0.69
Child	4	2.78
Parent	72	50.00
Sibling	51	35.42
Grandchildren	13	9.03
Other relatives	3	2.08
Employment Status		
No	51	35.42
Yes	15	10.42
Retired	21	14.58
Part-time (20 hours/week)	57	39.58
Educational Level		
No formal education	16	11.11
Primary school	31	21.53
Junior middle school	41	28.48
Senior middle school/polytechnic middle school	28	19.44
Bachelor degree/polytechnic high school	28	19.44

Monthly income (1 USD = 7.00 CNY)		
None	14	9.72
≤2,000 CNY	40	27.78
2,000-5,000 CNY	69	47.92
5,000-10,000 CNY	16	11.11
>10,000 CNY	5	3.47
Weekly frequency of transportation for patient to hemodialysis center		
One	8	5.55
Two	26	18.06
Three	108	75.00
Four	2	1.39
Duration been a caregiver (months) (\bar{X} =36.31 SD= 35.58 Range 6-156)		
<12 months	41	28.47
12-23 months	25	17.36
24-47 months	53	36.81
≥48 months	25	17.36
Daily caring hours (hours) (\bar{X} =17.65 SD= 7.98 Range 4-24)		
<5 hours/day	3	2.08
5-14 hours/day	55	38.19
≥ 15 hours/day	86	59.73
Chronic disease(s) status		
Yes	45	31.25
No	99	68.75
Type of the insurance for the patient		
None	2	1.39
Provincial one	40	27.78
Municipal one	50	34.72
The New Rural Cooperative Insurance (NRCI)	52	36.11
Co-morbidities beyond ESRD of the patient		
Yes	103	71.53
No	41	28.47
The number of dependents		
0	12	8.33
1	71	49.31
2	38	26.39
3	14	9.72
4	6	4.17
>4	3	2.08

Part II: The Caregiving Preparedness Among Caregivers of Persons Receiving Hemodialysis

The total preparedness score, assessed using the CPCS, ranged from 1 to 26, with a mean of 14.24 (SD = 5.24), as shown in Table 2. Regarding physical care, 20.14% of caregivers (29) felt unprepared, while 40.28% (58) felt somewhat prepared. For emotional needs, 47.92% (69) felt somewhat prepared, while 36.81% (53) and 34.72% (50) felt unprepared or only somewhat prepared for stress management. In offering related services, 35.42% (29) felt unprepared, but 43.06% (62) were somewhat prepared for entertainment activities. About 40 caregivers felt unprepared for emergencies, with 40.97% (59) feeling unprepared to seek help from the healthcare system. Among the eight sub-items, caregivers reported most prepared for "providing physical care" (mean = 2.15, SD = 1.02) and least prepared for "handling emergencies" (mean = 1.18, SD = 1.02). Detailed data are provided in Table 2.

Table 2: The Frequency and Percentage (%) of each item of the CPCS among Family Caregivers in Nanning City, Guangxi, China (n=144)

Item	Mean (SD)	Not at all n(%)	Not too well n(%)	Somewhat well n(%)	Pretty well n(%)	Very well n(%)
1.Prepared providing physical needs	2.15(1.02)	7(4.86)	29(20.14)	58(40.28)	35(24.31)	15(10.42)
2.Prepared providing emotional needs	1.88(0.88)	8(5.56)	36(25)	69(47.92)	26(18.06)	5(3.47)
3.Prepared offering related services	1.95(1.22)	12(8.33)	51(35.42)	36(25)	22(15.28)	23(15.97)
4.Prepared about stress management	1.62(0.95)	15(10.42)	53(36.81)	50(34.72)	23(15.97)	3(2.08)
5.Prepared activities for entertainment	2.06(0.98)	7(4.86)	32(22.22)	62(43.06)	31(21.53)	12(8.33)
6.Prepared managing emergencies	1.18(1.02)	40(27.78)	59(40.97)	24(16.67)	20(13.89)	1(0.69)
7.Prepared getting help and information from the healthcare system	1.59(0.88)	12(8.33)	59(40.97)	50(34.72)	21(14.58)	2(1.39)
8.Overall preparedness	1.77(0.79)	1(0.69)	56(38.89)	68(47.2)	13(9.03)	6(4.17)
Total CPCS \bar{X} =14.24 SD = 5.24 Median=14.50 Actual Range =1-26						

Part III: The Burden Among Caregivers of Persons Receiving Hemodialysis

The perceived burden scores, assessed via CZBI, ranged from 7 to 80 with a mean and SD of 50.25±17.65, as shown in Table 3. Regarding about the five domains, “Burden in relationship” ranged from 2 to 23 with mean ± SD of 13.33±5.45, “Emotional well-beings” ranged from 0 to 25 with mean ± SD of 14.97±6.07, “Social and family life” ranged from 0 to 16 with mean ± SD of 7.67±4.37, “Finances” ranged from 0 to 4 with mean ± SD of 2.91±1.29 and “Loss of control over one’s life” ranged from 0 to 16 with mean ± SD of 11.38±3.34. The experienced burden of 5 domains in sub-items, ranked from highest to lowest, was as follows: Finances, Loss of control over one’s life, Burden in relationship, Emotional well-beings and Social and family life, as shown in Table 3. Thus, family caregivers suffered most about financial burden and least on social and family burden.

Table 3: Mean, Standard Deviation, Median, Range of CZBI and Five Domains in Nanning City, Guangxi, China (n=144)

Five Domains / Overall Burden	Actual Range	Possible Range	Total Score Mean± SD	Total Score Median	Sub-items Mean± SD
Burden in relationship	2-23	0-24	13.33±5.45	13.38	2.22±0.91
Emotional well-beings	0-25	0-28	14.97±6.07	15.00	2.14±0.87
Social and family life	0-16	0-16	7.67±4.37	8.00	1.92±1.09
Finances	0-4	0-4	2.91±1.29	3.00	2.91±1.29
Loss of control over one’s life	1-16	0-16	11.38±3.34	12.00	2.84±0.84
Overall burden CZBI	7-80	0-88	50.25±17.65	53.00	-----

Part IV: The Relationship between Burden and Caregiving Preparedness Among Caregivers of Persons Receiving Hemodialysis

The relationship between burden and caregiving preparedness among caregivers of persons receiving hemodialysis is presented in Tables 4. The correlations between preparedness and burden in each including burden in relationship, emotional well-being, social and family life, finances, loss of control over one’s life, and overall burden are r = -0.373, r = -0.444, r = -0.430, r = -0.427, r = -

0.361 and $r = -0.474$, ($P < 0.01$) respectively. These results indicated a moderate negative relationship between caregiving preparedness and burden among caregivers of persons receiving HD.

Table 4: The Correlation between Preparedness and Burden in Nanning City, Guangxi, China (n=144)

Five Domains / Overall Burden	Preparedness (CPCS)	
	r	p-value
Burden in relationship	-.373 **	.000
Emotional well-beings	-.444 **	.000
Social and family life	-.430 **	.000
Finances	-.427 **	.000
Loss of control over one's life	-.361 **	.000
Overall Burden CZBI	-.474 **	.000

** $p < .01$. * $p < .05$.

DISCUSSION

Part I: The Caregiving Preparedness Among Caregivers of Persons Receiving Hemodialysis

The results indicate that the mean \pm SD of overall preparedness score (CPCS) among family caregivers was 14.24 ± 5.24 , suggesting the caregiving preparedness was relatively low. Notably, only 4 caregivers (2.78%) thought “very well prepared”, while the majority of caregivers (54.86%) reported “somewhat prepared”. Among all eight items of CPCS, the family caregivers reported least prepared to respond to and handle involved emergencies ($\bar{X} = 1.18$, $SD = 1.02$). It explained by 40 caregivers (27.78%) felt “not at all” and 59 ones (40.97%) felt “not too well prepared”, and only 1 caregiver (0.69%) felt “very well prepared” about handling emergencies. Conversely, they felt most prepared taking care of their family member's physical needs ($\bar{X} = 2.15$, $SD = 1.02$). It can be explained by 58 caregivers (40.28%) perceived “somewhat well prepared” and 35 caregivers (24.31%) felt “pretty well” with 15 more (10.42%) experienced “very well prepared” about providing physical care. This discrepancy may be attributed by the perceived caregivers’ confidence. When family caregivers feel adequately prepared, they believe they can support patient self-care maintenance, and this confidence enhances the overall outcomes to the patient's well-being (Vellone, et al., 2020).

Caregivers’ overall preparedness was “somewhat prepared” via CPCS. The similarity has been observed in other Asian studies about ESRD (Liu, 2017; Sari et al., 2020), stroke (Liu, 2018; Liu et al., 2020), cancer (Otto et al., 2021). However, this study contrasts with researches on American and European populations caring for heart failure patients with the CPS scores were 2.13 and 2.11 respectively, where preparedness was lower (Petruzzo et al., 2019; Vellone et al., 2020). It may be explained by caregivers' confidence, cultural influences, and caregiving experience influencing preparedness for caregiving. Effective nursing interventions and continuous education for family caregivers to improve their readiness also addressed it (Wen., et al., 2020).

The clinic related factors, caring length including frequency of weekly receiving HD, duration been a caregiver, and length of daily caregiving may also positively impact the wellness of experienced preparedness. On average, 78 caregivers (54.17%) had been in their role for more than 24 months and 86 individuals (59.73%) provided care more than 15 hours per day, and about 110 cases (76.39%) visited hospital more than 3 times weekly among this surveyed population. The duration of caregiving since diagnosis may also correlate with preparedness levels, as long-term caregivers tend to feel more prepared after gaining and accumulating experience and guidance from

healthcare professionals during frequent visits. Liu (2020) indicated that effective clinical education about caregiving for the caregivers improves the readiness of preparedness (Liu, et al., 2020).

On another hand, a small part of caregivers (2.78%) reported “very well prepared” to care for ESRD patients receiving hemodialysis. The perception may be influenced by several factors from this studying as following, majority of family caregivers are married (140, 97.20%) female (90, 62.50%) caregivers who were parents (72, 50%), well-educated, and potentially higher income (>10,000 CNY/month) (5, 3.47%). This demographic profile likely enhances the perceived preparedness which explained by some factors enhancing preparedness as follows, being a female parent, fewer caregiving hours per week, and high educational attainment (Petruzzo et al., 2019; Hagedoorn et al., 2020). Female caregivers, naturally inclined to care for ill family members, tend to become more confident and feel more prepared (Vellone et al., 2020).

This study revealed family caregivers felt the most prepared about “taking care of their family member's physical needs” ($\bar{X} = 2.15$, $SD = 1.02$) and the least prepared about “managing the emergencies” ($\bar{X} = 1.18$, $SD = 1.02$). Chinese researcher Liu (2018) got the similar results among the targeted population with stroke (Liu., 2018). Several factors may be attributed to this result, possibly linked to demographic characteristics such as age and educational background. Another explanation may be benefits through a series of medical activities from professional healthcare providers who are dedicated to meet patients’ needs by offering knowledge and coping strategies. In this study, caregivers’ age ranged from 21 to 79 years with a mean \pm SD is 52.38 ± 14.23 years, about 52 individuals (36.11%) are old adults aged 60-79, along with 45 cases (31.25%) reported living with chronic diseases requiring daily medication. Older caregivers often experience reduced energy and functional health, which may impact their preparedness for caregiving. As older adults, they may also worry about their own declined physical conditions (Petruzzo et al., 2019). Moreover, 72.00% of caregivers had educational qualifications below a bachelor's degree, with 16 caregivers (11.10%) having no formal education. Previous research indicates that demographic characteristics, acquired medical knowledge, and caregiving experience predict levels of wellness of preparedness (Liu et al., 2020). Hagedoorn et al. (2020) noted that educational level significantly affects caregiving preparedness; caregivers with higher education or training tend to perceive themselves as better prepared (Henriksson & Arestedt., 2013). Caregivers felt least prepared about “managing the emergencies” ($\bar{X} = 1.18$, $SD = 1.02$) may also caused by the uncertainty of disease. Of the 144 involved patients, 103 cases (71.53%) had comorbidities in addition to ESRD. The severity of these comorbidities was linked to caregivers' preparedness levels (Liu et al., 2020). Family caregivers may struggle to predict the symptoms and signs of ESRD deterioration and appropriate responses from healthcare professionals, especially in emergency occasions, leading to increased stress, burnout, and concerns for their loved ones, all impacting their preparedness. Additionally, patients with comorbidities or chronic illnesses may exhibit lower levels of preparedness, particularly in emergency situations, necessitating tailored professional guidance, especially among groups with lower income, poorer mental health, or lacking of marital support (Wang et al., 2021).

Part II: The Burden Among Caregivers of Persons Receiving Hemodialysis

Caregivers' self-assessed burden scores ranged from 7 to 80, with a mean \pm SD of overall CZBI is 50.25 ± 17.65 . The caregivers experienced the most financial burden ($\bar{X} = 2.91$, $SD = 1.29$) compared to others, while social family burden ($\bar{X} = 1.92$, $SD = 1.09$) was the least significant one.

These results may be explained by the following details. In response to item No. 22 ($\bar{X} = 3.05$, $SD = 1.05$) about overall burden, 64 caregivers (44.44%) selected "Always" and 40 cases (27.78%) chose "Often". This suggested that a significant proportion of caregivers (104, 72.22%) experience substantial burdens associated with caring for patients with ESRD. This overall burden may link to

above demographic information and characteristics of the caregivers impact the level of family burden, such as age, income, and education. Due to limited educational backgrounds, the care providers believe themselves to lack updated medical knowledge and practical nursing skills for managing ESRD at home. These findings are aligned with numerous studies conducted across different populations in recent years. Chinese researchers Li (2017) and Fu (2018) reported the majority of family caregivers had lower educational attainment (below a diploma of bachelor or polytechnic high school), were unemployed or worked part-time with low income ($\leq 1,990$ CNY/month) (Fu, 2018; Li et al., 2017). Therefore, seeking professional guidance from health-workers are needed.

The majority of the caregivers suffered from financial burden ($\bar{X} = 2.91$, $SD = 1.28$) highest among 5 domains. This finding was supported by the item No.15 addressed in the financial domain. It indicated a total of 101 family caregivers (70.14%), with 36 individuals (25%) responded “Always” and 65 caregivers (45.14%) responded “Often”, perceived a significant financial burden. This situation underscores a need to address the current state of insurance coverage. Despite 98.61% of the targeted patients got different national medical insurances, which is higher than the decreasing national ratio of 95% (National Healthcare Security Administration, 2023), low-income and rural freelancers often struggle to timely pay the basic bill for national medical insurance. The Chinese Hierarchical Healthy Insurance System, launched since 1998, has becoming a key source of assistance for medical payment covering part of the costs associated with maintained HD (Wang & Long, 2022). However, the national insurance covers 50-90% of the medical bills in Guangxi, which is lower the annual increasing national one of 79.8-89.2% (National Healthcare Security Administration, 2023). Furthermore, there is an annual funding limit of 220,000 CNY for each HD patient (Department of Human Resources and Social Security of Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, 2016). Additionally, caregivers with lower income level experience a higher degree of financial burden. Hemodialysis costs approximately 400-600 CNY per session, with 76.4% of patients undergoing 12 to 16 times per month. Family caregivers also incur additional expenses for medications, transportation, specific diets, and daily nursing care of tube and AV fistula, and so on (Anderson & Nguyen, 2018). Lastly, the COVID-19 pandemic partly explained the highest financial burden, as income declines affecting families particularly those caring for individuals with chronic diseases like ESRD. The global economic slowdown may further force many family caregivers to limit their daily expenses (Kaur., & Latha., 2022). Therefore, insufficient medical insurances, low income, high costs and emergency event of COVID pandemic all attribute significantly to the high financial burden experienced by the family caregivers. Thereby, to alleviate this heavy financial burden especially for families with low and middle incomes, multi-solutions are all needed, including financial support from government and private organizations, free transportation, cost-effective facility of treatment, and subsidies for related medications (Hosen., Nafiujjaman., & Nishat., 2022).

The caregivers reported least burden about “Social and family life burden” ($\bar{X} = 7.67$, $SD = 4.37$). It indicates they received a degree of positive support from social family. This can be explained by demographic factors such as marital status, medical payment methods as current improvements in insurance coverage, and the relationships and understanding fostered within society and family. The majority of caregivers were married (140, 97.22%) and most of the HD patients (142, 98.61%) benefited from national insurance coverage through direct payment methods via the help from family. Similarity was observed in another South-China study about overall family functioning, identified middle and young adult patients demonstrated moderate and above average family functioning ($p < .05$) (Wu et al., 2019). Furthermore, perceived social family support plays a partial mediating role between caregiver burden and positive coping strategies among family caregivers ($p < .05$) (Liu., 2017).

Part III: The Relationship Between Burden and Caregiving Preparedness Among Family Caregivers

The statistical result found a moderate negative correlation between self-reported overall burden and acquired preparedness for caregiving ($r = -.474, p = .000$) among the family caregivers of persons undergoing hemodialysis. It was assumed that caregivers who are well-prepared for caregiving would experience a lower caregiver burden, and vice versa. Firstly, it directly reported from this study that totally 95 caregivers felt not well prepared, with the details of 16 (11.11%) caregivers got total score from 1 to 8 and 79 (54.86%) scored 9 to 16. On another side, the total burden score of Mean \pm SD is 50.25 ± 17.65 , which revealed that caregivers experienced a relatively high caregiver burden. Secondly, it would be supported by the demographic data from this population. Notably, 97.22% of caregivers were married, indicating that many were balancing caregiving role with other family obligations. This dual responsibility may exacerbate the caregiver burden, as caregivers are often required to manage both their own family's needs and the complex demands of caring for a patient undergoing hemodialysis. Additionally, this result could be also explained by local cultural difference about minority in Guangxi, which can influence caregiving experiences, including reactions to the ESRD, coping strategies, and attitudes toward caregiving. Lastly, it may also be attributed by the increased confidence of caregivers that stems from a supportive nursing model and an effective medical system that provides targeted support and tailored guidance. The key medical interventions including implementing psychological education, enhanced caregiving training, offering social support, remote intervention, and ongoing evaluations (Wang., Yi., & Fan., 2024). When caregivers are likely to feel more capable of addressing the needs of ESRD patients and navigating the complexities of home-care through the comprehensive supportive networks, their confidence rises up, leading to reduced anxiety and stress, by which in turn to a lower perception of perceived burden. Similar findings have been supported by recent studies across different populations. For instance, a study in a palliative care unit in Turkiye observed a negative correlation ($p < 0.01$) between caregiving preparedness ($\bar{X} = 18.55, SD = 6.83$) and burden ($\bar{X} = 33.6, SD = 13.03$) (Karabulutlu., Turan., & Yanmiş., 2022). A multicenter cross-sectional survey of caregivers for individuals with disabilities resulting from stroke, spinal cord injury, or traumatic brain injury, identified a significant negative correlation ($r_s = -.512, p < 0.001$) between preparedness ($\bar{X} = 2.10, SD = 0.90$) and burden ($\bar{X} = 34.70, SD = 19.1$) (Uhm et al., 2023).

This study revealed moderate negative correlations between preparedness and each domain including relationship burden ($r = -.373, p = .000$), emotional burden ($r = -.444, p = .000$), social and family burden ($r = -.43, p = .000$), financial burden ($r = -.427, p = .000$), and loss of control over one's life ($r = -.361, p = .000$). Access to supportive networks such as professional healthcare services, public resources, and social community and family, can partly help alleviate the strains associated with caregiving. Emotional resilience enables them to effectively cope with the stresses of their roles. As they manage their emotions better, they may perceive caregiving experience as less burdensome. National and social backups can also significantly reduce the financial challenges related to the budget of treatment, diet and other activities, thereby building up more confidence to the caregivers.

Conversely, a study on informal (unpaid) caregiving provided to patients with traumatic brain injury found no significant relationship between caregiver burden and preparedness ($p > .05$) (Lieshout et al., 2020). The probable cause is caregivers get limited resources to be well prepared in an emergency situation about caregiving. Despite varying findings regarding the relationship between preparedness and burden, it is generally recognized that thorough preparation across caregiving domains tends to contribute to lower self-reported caregiving burden. Caregivers who feel well prepared in all aspects of caregiving often exhibit higher levels of confidence. Thus, when caregivers feel well prepared across different domains, such as burden in the relationship, emotional well-beings,

social and family life, finances, and loss of control over one's life, they intend to perceive caregiving as less burdensome and are able to fulfill their caregiving role more smoothly.

IMPLICATIONS

The study provides fundamental information with guided insights to better understand and enhance clinical practice and homecare by promoting preparedness at Guangxi hospital in order to reduce the caregiving burden. Clinical nursing staffs as the primary contacts for patients and their families, are well positioned to support informal caregivers, especially in emergency response, stress management, emotional support, and healthcare related services. The findings indicate that enhancing preparedness can potentially reduce caregiver burden. Therefore, the nurses can utilize this study to guide caregiving dynamics, coordinate with medical teams, and connect families to financial aid and public resources.

FUTURE RESEARCH

Future research should investigate the effectiveness of specific interventions aimed at enhancing caregiver preparedness and reducing burden, would provide valuable insights into best practices for caregiving support.

Human Rights (Ethics)

The study and data collection was designed to protect participants' rights in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. The research proposal was approved by the Faculty of Nursing Research Ethics Committee at Chiang Mai University and the Institutional Review Board (2022-EXP078 numbered). Confidentiality was assured, with responses anonymized using code numbers. To prevent COVID-19 transmission, both the researcher and participants followed the Guangxi Hospital's COVID-19 control guidelines.

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